

Household religion at Ur

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Ur, modern Tell el-Muqayyar, in southern Iraq, is one of the most ancient cities of Mesopotamia; it hosted a very important cult complex dedicated to the Moon-God – Nanna in Sumerian, Suen in Akkadian – including a temple, a ziqqurat and residences for the king and the high priestess. Two extended quarters of private houses, dating from the beginning of the 2nd millennium BCE were brought to light; they are quite well preserved and many of them featured burials under their floors. Of particular interest are some built underground tombs: according to L. Woolley, their excavator, these tombs were related to large rooms, with special features interpreted as cult installations, and with the largest room of the house, interpreted as a reception room. The final interpretation was that at Ur they practiced funerary cults for the ancestors in private chapels, accessible to the members of the household and to their guests. Upon a new analysis of the evidence, it was observed that the connection between built tombs and chapels was not a constant element: in 15 houses there were chapels only; in 15 houses the chapel was related with a tomb; in 17 houses there were the tombs but no chapel. Chapels for private cults are also attested in the same period at Nippur, Tell Asmar and Tell Brak, but they are not associated with tombs. The chapels feature altars ca. 50 cm high and structures looking like miniature temples, up to 1.40 m high; a hearth with a long chimney reaching to the roof was interpreted as an incense-burner. The main interpretations for these chapels are: 1) places for funerary cults (to be dismissed for the lack of a constant correlation with tombs); 2) cult for "family gods" (doubtful because minor gods had their small temples within the domestic quarters); 3) places for private ceremonies connecting the extended family and other social groups to enhance social bonds, for instance for marriages and/or economic contracts.

Date Range: 2000 BCE - 1800 BCE

Region: Ur III core

Region tags: Southern Iraq, Al-Qadisiyah, Southern Mesopotamia

Core region of the Ur III kingdom roughly between 2100 and 2000 BC.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: C.L. Woolley, *Ur Excavations VII. The Old Babylonian Period*, Philadelphia-London 1976
- Source 2: F. Pinnock, "Private Chapels" in Southern Mesopotamia at the Beginning of the Second Millennium BC, in J.M. Evans and E. Rossberger (eds), *Ancient Near Eastern Temple Inventories in the Third and Second Millennia BCE*, Gladbeck 2019, pp. 119-129
- Source 3: P. Brusasco, *The Archaeology of Verbal and Nonverbal Meaning. Mesopotamian Domestic Architecture and Its Textual Dimensions*, Oxford 2007

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <http://www.ur-online.org/>

– Source 1 Description: Official website by the British Museum

Notes: None

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: CDLI - Cuneiform Digital Library InitiativeA

– Source 1 Description: A corpus of published cuneiform documents

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– I don't know

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– I don't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– I don't know

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– No

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– No

Is iconography present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– I don't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

↳ Personal effects:

– Yes

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

↳ Significant wealth (e.g. gold, jade, intensely worked objects):

– No

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

↳ Other valuable/precious items interred:

– No

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

↳ As cenotaphs:

– No

↳ In cemetery:

– No

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Yes [specify]: The king has to fulfil the gods' wishes and his power and actions are

determined by the gods, in particular by the main deity of the town. In the case of Ur the main god is the Moon-God Nanna/Suen

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– No

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

- ↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can reward:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god can punish:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:
 - Yes
- ↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:
 - Yes
- ↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:
 - Field doesn't know

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

↳ In trance possession:

– No

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– No

Notes: Religious specialists are present and help the people to interpret their dreams or to understand omens

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Notes: The king uses the specialists, too

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Natural phenomena or strange events, like the birth of an animal with some peculiarity

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– Yes

- ↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:
 - Yes

- ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - Yes

 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - No

 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - No

 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes

 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes

 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - Yes

 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings knows your basic character (personal essence):
 - Yes

 - ↳ Non-human supernatural beings know what will happen to you, what

you will do (future sight):

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– No

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can reward:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings can punish:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– No

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– No

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

- ↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:
 - Yes
- ↳ Organized hierarchically:
 - Yes
- ↳ Power of beings is domain specific:
 - Yes
- ↳ Other organization for pantheon:
 - No

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

- ↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously “moral” or “ethical” norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

 - Yes
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:
 - No

- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:
 - No
- ↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:
 - Yes

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– No

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– I don't know

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– I don't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– I don't know

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– I don't know

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– I don't know

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– I don't know

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– I don't know

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Notes: Households produced a part of their food in orchards and fields close to the town, whereas the main core of their subsistence was provided by the central authority by means of the redistribution system.

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Pastoralism
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Trade on the middle and long distance

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

- Pastoralism
- Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)
- Other [specify in comments]

Notes: Trade on the middle and long distance

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Household religion at Ur, Woolley, Carl Leonard. Ur Excavation VII. The Old Babylonian Period. Philadelphia - London: British Museum, 1976.